

CLASSROOM STRATEGIES OF MULTIGRADE TEACHERS AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENTS OF THE PUPILS IN MAIGO DISTRICT

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 21

Issue 1

Pages: 80-88

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1943

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12186933

Manuscript Accepted: 05-10-2024

Classroom Strategies of Multigrade Teachers and Academic Achievements of the Pupils in Maigo District

Karen Gay P. Dy,* Aisah V. Borerros, Ruskein D. Burlat, Markhiesvel L. Dicalan,
Jaica R. Malon, Manilyn M. Marturillas

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study aimed to analyze the effectiveness of differentiated instruction, collaborative learning, and flexible groupings on the academic achievements of pupils in multi-grade classrooms during the 2022-2023 school year. Five multi-grade teachers from various schools in the district were purposively chosen, along with 230 pupils, utilizing a descriptive correlational design. The data were analyzed using means, standard deviation, frequency counts, and Pearson product correlation at a significance level of 0.05. The findings indicate that the majority of respondents perceive differentiated instruction, collaborative learning, and flexible groupings as highly effective strategies. Additionally, a significant proportion of pupils demonstrate satisfactory academic achievements, with many falling within the "Very Satisfactory" GPA range. Pearson correlation analysis reveals a strong positive relationship between differentiated instruction and academic achievement, underscoring the importance of tailoring teaching methods to individual student needs. In conclusion, understanding the effectiveness of multi-grade teaching strategies can provide valuable insights for educators and policymakers. By acknowledging the positive impact of differentiated instruction and other collaborative strategies on academic achievement, educators can better support multi-grade teachers and learners in achieving academic success.

Keywords: *differentiated instruction, collaborative learning, and flexible groupings*

Introduction

The concept of multi-grade teaching involves a single educator overseeing multiple grade levels concurrently (Little, 2001). This approach accommodates students of varying ages within one learning environment. In the Philippines, the Department of Education has instituted policies outlined in DepEd Order No.96, s.1997, governing the structure and operation of multi-grade classes. This initiative aims to mitigate educational disparities by ensuring accessibility regardless of geographical location or circumstances. Furthermore, the implementation of multi-grade education in the Philippines received reinforcement through DO 81, s. 2009. This governmental support includes provisions for special hardship allowances, comprehensive training programs for multi-grade instructors, distribution of resource packages, and additional benefits. The multi-grade classroom model diverges from traditional organization methods, as it integrates students from multiple grade levels into a single instructional setting.

In traditional educational setups, students typically progress through grades according to their age. However, the dynamics shift in multi-grade classrooms where grade level repetition and acceleration are prevalent. This educational model is gaining traction globally, yet the scarcity of research on optimal teaching methodologies within multi-grade environments poses a significant challenge for educators (Hawes & Placier, 2018). According to a study by Hawes and Placier (2018), teachers in multi-grade classrooms often struggle to meet the diverse learning needs of their pupils, which can lead to lower academic achievement for some pupils. Research has shown that multi-grade classrooms can be challenging for teachers because they require a more individualized approach to instruction (Dyson, 2013). This can be difficult for teachers who are used to teaching in single-grade classrooms and may not have the necessary training or support to meet the needs of students with different abilities and learning styles (Dyson, 2013).

A study conducted in the Philippines found that learners in multi-grade classrooms achieved similar levels of academic success as pupils in single-grade classrooms (Aparicio & Rappa, 2013). Another study conducted in the United

States found that multi-grade classrooms had higher levels of learners' engagement and achievement than single-grade classrooms (Inman & Marlowe, 2019). However, there is a lack of research on the specific strategies that can be used to improve academic achievement in multi-grade classrooms.

Despite the existing research on multi-grade teaching, there is a limited focus on the strategies that can improve academic achievement in multi-grade classrooms. (Aparicio & Rappa, 2013; Hawkrigde, 2015). Therefore, there is a need for further investigation into the specific classroom strategies that can enhance academic achievement in multi-grade classrooms. To fill this gap, this research aims to examine the strategies used in multi-grade classrooms, and their impact on elementary learners' academic achievement. (Inman & Marlowe, 2019, Stolp & Smith, 2016).

Classroom strategies refer to the various methods and techniques that teachers use to promote learning and achieve instructional goals. These classrooms require teachers to cater to the needs of learners with varying abilities across multiple grade levels, making it challenging to provide effective instruction. According to a study by the National Center for Education Statistics (NCES), over 10% of public schools in the United States have multi-grade classrooms (NCES, 2019). Given the prevalence of multi-grade classrooms, it is crucial to explore the classroom strategies used by teachers in these settings and their impact on academic achievement. Research

has shown that effective classroom strategies can positively impact academic achievement. In a study by de Kock and Basson (2015), it was found that multi-grade classrooms can be effective in improving academic achievement, but only when teachers use appropriate instructional strategies. The study found that teachers who used strategies such as differentiated instruction, collaborative learning and flexible groupings were better able to meet the needs of their pupils and improve academic achievement.

Differentiated Instructions defined as changing the pace, level, or kind of instruction you provide in response to individual learners' needs, styles, or interests (Hencox, 2012). Teachers use a variety of teaching and learning strategies that are necessary to meet the diverse needs of learners.

A study by Kaur (2021) found that collaborative learning had a positive impact on academic achievement among students in multi-grade classrooms. Researchers believe that collaborative learning involves organizing individuals with varying levels of skills into pairs, groups, or teams that compete with each other, with the aim of promoting more productive cooperation.

Flexible groupings involve grouping learners based on their academic needs and abilities (Slavin, 1995). A study by Kim and Kim (2020) found that flexible grouping was an effective strategy for improving academic achievement among low-performing pupils.

Vygotsky's scaffolding theory emphasizes the role of social interaction and support in the learning process. In a multi-grade teaching environment, where students of different ages and abilities are grouped together, scaffolding becomes crucial (Vygotsky, 1978). Older or more advanced students can provide support and guidance to younger or less experienced peers, creating a collaborative learning environment. This reciprocal teaching dynamic not only reinforces the learning of both parties but also fosters a sense of community and cooperation within the classroom. Moreover, teachers can employ scaffolding techniques to tailor instruction to individual students' needs, ensuring that each student receives the appropriate level of support to progress academically.

Gardner's Multiple Intelligences theory posits that individuals possess different cognitive strengths and learning styles (Gardner, 1983). In a multi-grade classroom, where students come from diverse backgrounds and possess varying levels of ability, acknowledging and accommodating these differences is essential for promoting academic achievement. Teachers can leverage Gardner's theory to design instruction that appeals to a range of intelligences, ensuring that all students have opportunities to excel based on their unique strengths. By incorporating activities that cater to different intelligences, such as hands-on projects for kinesthetic learners or visual aids for spatial learners, teachers can create a more inclusive learning environment where all students can thrive.

In summary, Vygotsky's scaffolding theory highlights the importance of social interaction and support in multi-grade classrooms, while Gardner's Multiple Intelligences theory underscores the need to recognize and address the diverse learning needs of students. By applying these theories within the context of multi-grade teaching, educators can create enriching learning experiences that promote academic achievement for all students, regardless of their age or ability level.

Pupil's academic achievements refer to the extent to which pupils have attained the learning objectives set out for them within an academic setting. One definition of academic achievement comes from the National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP) program in the United States, which defines it as "the level of knowledge and skills attained by students in core academic subjects, as measured by standardized assessments" (National Center for Education Statistics, 2018). A review of literature on academic achievement by the National Research Council found that there are many factors that contribute to a student's academic success, including family background, peer groups, and school resources (National Research Council, 2004).

Academic achievements are typically measured through a range of assessments, including exams, tests, essays, and coursework, and are used to evaluate a student's progress and potential for success. Thus, academic achievement can be measured through grades or grade point average (GPA).

The scaffolding theory developed by Lev Vygotsky, which emphasizes the importance of social interaction and guidance in the learning process, is particularly relevant for diverse classrooms such as those found in multi-grade classes. (Smagorinsky, 2018). Acknowledging and embracing the diversity in the classroom can lead to successful collaboration and learning. By providing temporary support to pupils, teachers can help them move beyond their current level of competence and become independent pupils.

The theory of Multiple Intelligences can serve as a theoretical framework for the study "Multi-grade Classroom Strategies of the Teachers and Academic Achievements of the Pupils in Maigo District". This framework can be used to guide the investigation of the impact of teachers' use of multiple intelligences- based strategies on the academic achievement of elementary students in multi- grade classrooms. In this study, Multiple Intelligences can be used to categorize the different strengths and preferences for learning among students in multi- grade classrooms. Teachers can then use this information to design and implement teaching strategies that cater to these different intelligences, promoting student engagement and academic achievements.

The researchers were interested in conducting the study in the second quarter of the school year 2022–2023 with the multi-grade teachers of different multi-grade schools under Maigo, Lanao District. In relation to this study, the researchers aimed to determine whether the teachers' multi-grade classroom strategies had a significant relationship on the academic achievement of the pupils in a multi-grade classroom setting. This research stemmed from the recognition that, despite challenging teaching scenarios for multi-grade teachers, positive outcomes persisted. By exploring the effectiveness of various teaching approaches, educators could make informed decisions about supporting learning and growth optimally.

The researchers believed that this study could have inspired multi-grade teachers to employ classroom strategies that enhance the academic achievement of elementary pupils in multi-grade classrooms. The study was intended to serve as a benchmark for future multi-grade teachers, providing insights into how to manage their classes effectively. Its objective was to ascertain the classroom strategies utilized by teachers in handling multi-grade classes efficiently and to present specific strategies applicable in teaching within rural area settings.

Research Questions

The study aimed to determine Multi-grade Classroom Strategies of the Teacher's and Academic Achievements of the Pupils in Maigo District for the second grading, Academic Year 2022-2023. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How effective are the classroom strategies employed by teachers overseeing multi-grade classes in terms of differentiated instruction, collaborative learning, and flexible grouping?
2. What are the academic achievements of the pupils in terms of grade point average during the second grading of school year 2022-2023?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the classroom strategies used by multi-grade teachers in the differentiated instruction, collaborative learning, flexible groupings and academic achievement of the pupils?

Methodology

Research Design

To ensure the validity and reliability of the study's findings, the variables were carefully measured and operationalized using a combination of methods within a descriptive-correlational research design.

Firstly, the researchers identified the variables of interest: teachers' multi-grade classroom strategies and pupils' academic achievement in the academic year 2022-2023 among elementary pupils. These variables were operationalized by defining specific aspects of multi-grade classroom strategies (such as differentiated instruction, collaborative learning, and flexible grouping) and academic achievement (such as standardized test scores, grades, and teacher evaluations).

The chosen research design, descriptive-correlational, allowed for the systematic investigation of the relationship between these variables without inferring direct cause-and-effect relationships. This aligns with the nature of correlational research, as described by Bhandari (2022).

To measure teachers' multi-grade classroom strategies, an adopted and modified structured questionnaire was utilized. This questionnaire likely included items or scales related to the specific strategies being investigated, such as questions about how often teachers implement differentiated instruction techniques or facilitate collaborative learning activities.

For assessing pupils' academic achievement, various indicators may have been employed, such as standardized test scores, grades in specific subjects, or teacher evaluations of academic progress. These indicators provide objective and subjective measures of academic achievement, offering a comprehensive understanding of pupils' performance.

In addition to structured questionnaires, interview questions were likely used to gather qualitative data, providing deeper insights into teachers' and pupils' experiences with multi-grade classroom strategies and academic achievement. Open-ended questions in both the questionnaire and interviews further enhanced the validity and reliability of the study's findings by allowing participants to express nuanced perspectives and experiences. By employing multiple methods of data collection and carefully defining and operationalizing variables, the researchers ensured that the study's findings were robust, valid, and reliable.

Participants

The participants in that study were multi-grade teachers from various schools in Maigo District during the academic year 2022-2023. The researchers visited elementary schools in the Maigo district and identified a total of 15 multi- grade teachers, who were chosen as respondents for the research:

<i>Multi-grade School/s</i>	<i>No. of Multi-grade Teachers</i>	<i>Total Number Of Respondents</i>
Baybay Kulasihan Elementary School	Grades 1 to 6	5
Villanueva Kulasihan Elementary School	Grades 1 to 4	3
Santa Cruz Elementary School	Grades 1 to 6	4
Maliwanag Primary School	Grades 1 to 4	3
Total		15

The selection of participants for the study involved careful consideration of criteria to ensure their representativeness of the target population.

Firstly, all 15 multi-grade teachers in Maigo District were chosen as participants. This decision was based on the recognition that these

teachers are directly involved in implementing multi-grade classroom strategies and have firsthand experience with the dynamics of such instructional environments. By including all teachers within the district, the study aimed to capture a comprehensive overview of multi-grade teaching practices.

Furthermore, the selection of schools within Maigo District was strategic to ensure diversity and representation across different geographical areas. Specifically, five teachers were chosen from Baybay Kulasihan Elementary School, three from Villanueva Kulasihan Elementary School, four from Santa Cruz Elementary School, and three from Maliwanag Primary School. This distribution ensured that teachers from various locations within the district were included, accounting for potential differences in resources, student demographics, and community dynamics.

In addition to selecting teachers, the study also involved purposively choosing 230 pupils to represent the academic achievement aspect of the investigation. Purposive sampling was employed to select pupils who were deemed most relevant to the research objectives, likely based on criteria such as grade level, academic performance, and demographic diversity. This approach ensured that the selected pupils provided meaningful insights into the relationship between teachers' multi-grade classroom strategies and academic achievement.

Overall, by including all multi-grade teachers in Maigo District and purposively selecting pupils representing diverse academic backgrounds, the study aimed to enhance the representativeness of the sample and provide a comprehensive understanding of the research phenomenon within the target population.

Instruments

In this study, data was collected through a survey questionnaire, which had been adopted and modified for the research. The questionnaire's content was derived and adjusted from previous works, with Leung (2014) having influenced the questions related to differentiated instruction, Mohan and Rathor (2016) having guided the section on collaborative learning, and Bonner and Miller (2013) having shaped the part concerning flexible grouping. The questionnaire statements were intentionally crafted to be clear and concise, ensuring that respondents could easily provide answers while remaining relevant to the study's objective of assessing the efficacy of multi-grade teachers' classroom strategies.

The first section prompted respondents to answer questions, utilizing a guideline questionnaire within the survey to specify their level of agreement with the statements. This section focused on multi-grade classroom strategies, and the indicators were rated on a four-point scale (4 strongly agree, 3 agree, 2 disagree, and 1 strongly disagree).

Scoring Indicator for the level of effectiveness of Classroom Strategies

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation
4	3.50 - 4.00	Strongly Agree	Very effective
3	2.50 - 3.9	Agree	Effective
2	1.50 - 1.49	Disagree	Less Effective
1	1.00 - 1.749	Strongly Disagree	Not Effective

The data for the pupils General Average for SY 2022 - 2023 was obtained from the school personnel (teacher) which was approved by the school principal. They were categorized based on the grading system of the Mindanao State University. The data on the academic performance of pupils were analyzed using the following scale:

Grading Scale	Qualifying Description	Qualifying Statement
90-100	Outstanding	Exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills and understanding can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic task.
85-89	Very Satisfactory	Develop the fundamental knowledge, skills and understanding can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic task.
80-84	Satisfactory	Develop the fundamental knowledge, skills and understanding with little guidance from the teacher and can transfer these understandings through authentic task.
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	Possesses the minimum knowledge, skills and core understandings but needs help throughout the authentic task.
Below 75	Did not meet expectation	Struggles with understanding the prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and skills.

Procedure

The data collection process commenced with a formal request for permission from the principal's office, seeking approval to conduct research with the designated respondents. Upon approval, the researchers personally administered the questionnaire, utilizing an adapted and modified version. The questionnaire was distributed to multi-grade teachers in Maigo District.

The data-gathering phase was scheduled for three (3) weeks, allowing ample time for both respondents and researchers to complete and distribute the questionnaire. To enhance the study's validity, respondents were also asked to respond to five (5) open-ended

questions related to multi-grade classroom strategies.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools will be used to analyze and interpret the data:

Mean and Standard Deviation. This we're used to analyze every response of the respondents regarding the level of effectiveness of multi-grade classroom strategies and academic achievement of the pupils.

Pearson r Correlation. This was used to determine the significant relationship between the independent variables and dependent variables.

Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and the Shapiro-Wilk test. These we're most widely used methods to test the normality of the data. The Shapiro-Wilk test is more appropriate method for small sample sizes (<50 samples) although it can also be handling on larger sample size while Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is used for $n \geq 50$. For both of the above tests, null hypothesis states that data are taken from normal distributed population.

Ethical Considerations

To address potential biases and ensure the confidentiality of participant responses, the researchers implemented several measures throughout the study:

Meticulous Record-Keeping: The researchers maintained detailed records of all aspects of the research process, including participant selection, data collection methods, and analysis procedures. This transparency helped mitigate potential biases and ensured the integrity of the research.

Adherence to Research Regulations: Throughout the research journey, the researchers strictly adhered to ethical guidelines and research regulations. This commitment ensured that the study was conducted ethically and responsibly, minimizing the risk of bias or misconduct.

Respect for Participant Confidentiality: Participants' responses were treated with the utmost confidentiality. The researchers ensured that participant identities were anonymized and that any personal information provided was kept confidential. This safeguarding of participant data helped protect individuals and schools from potential harm or repercussions.

Informed Consent Process: Prior to participating in the study, all participants were provided with clear and comprehensive information about the research objectives, procedures, and potential risks and benefits. They were given the opportunity to ask questions and provide voluntary informed consent to participate. This process ensured that participants understood the nature of the study and voluntarily agreed to take part without coercion or pressure.

Ethical Concerns Addressed Promptly: Throughout the study, the researchers remained vigilant for any ethical concerns that may have arisen. Any issues or conflicts were addressed promptly and transparently, with a commitment to resolving them in accordance with ethical principles and guidelines.

Confidentiality Pledge: The researchers made a solemn pledge to uphold the confidentiality of participant responses and sources. They refrained from using or disclosing any information provided in confidence, thereby respecting the trust placed in them by participants and maintaining the integrity of the research process.

Results and Discussion

This chapter explains the analysis and interpretation of the data gathered wherein the results are presented in tabular form followed by the discussion, analysis, and its interpretation. The chapter explains all the data gathered after utilizing and administering the deemed appropriate statistical tool used as stated in the preceding chapter.

Problem 1. What is the level of effectiveness of classroom strategies used by multi-grade teachers in the differentiated instruction, collaborative learning, and flexible grouping?

Table 1. shows the level of effectiveness of classroom strategies used by multi-grade teachers in the differentiated instruction, collaborative learning, and flexible grouping. The result indicates that classroom activities in terms of Differentiated instruction, collaborative learning and flexible grouping had a qualifying description of Agree. The result indicates that three strategies were very effective to pupils.

As revealed in the interview, Majority of the teachers shared that their knowledge on how to use of Differentiated instruction, cooperative learning and flexible grouping strategies really help the pupils' academic achievement since this topic was also included during the school learning action cells. Many teachers were trained by the DepEd, and re-echo to their co-teachers.

Moreover, the highest among the three strategies are differentiated instruction. Teachers rated (mean=3.81) "strongly agree" on the use of differentiated instruction. This means that they really believed that differentiated instruction is very effective strategies for pupils.

The use of these three classroom strategies plays an integral role in achieving significant improvements in the productivity of the pupils. Strategies like differentiated instruction, collaborative learning and flexible grouping, expands the learning experience and builds 21st century skills needed by the pupils. These will increase the pupil's engagement and motivation in the class and make them become more focused and attentive in the class discussions (Grabe,2019).

Table 1. *Mean and Standard Deviation of Classroom Activities in terms of Differentiated Instruction, Collaborative Learning and Flexible Grouping*

<i>Classroom Activities</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
Differentiated instruction	3.81	.15	SA	Very Effective
Collaborative Learning	3.53	.58	SA	Very Effective
Flexible Grouping	3.57	.66	SA	Very Effective

Legend: Advanced – 3.50-4.00- Strongly Agree, 2.50-3.49- Agree; 1.50-2.49 Disagree; below 1.49 Strongly Disagree

Kaur (2021) and Becker, et. Al (2018). found that collaborative learning, differentiated instruction and collaborative learning had a positive impact on academic achievement among pupils in multi-grade classrooms. Researchers believe that collaborative learning involves organizing individuals with varying levels of skills into pairs, groups, or teams that compete with each other, with the aim of promoting more productive cooperation.

Mastering these strategies was enough for someone to be considered a good teacher. Teacher could teach the students with the use of these strategies for they are expected to be able to integrate the strategies for teaching needs. These strategies are stipulated in the PPST to effective teachers as one of the included strategies to enhance teachers' teaching performance so that students can fully benefit in the teaching and learning process.

Problem 2. What is the academic achievement of the pupils in terms of grade point average during the second grading of school year 2022-2023?

Table 2 presents the pupils academic achievement of the 230 pupils based from their 2nd grading cards during S.Y. 2022-2023. On the average, the pupils obtained an academic achievement of 86.8 which is qualitatively described as very satisfactory.

Table 2. *Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Pupils' Academic Achievement*

<i>O</i>		<i>VS</i>		<i>S</i>		<i>FS</i>		<i>DMS</i>		<i>Average</i>
<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>N=230</i>
22	9	96	42	89	39	23	10	0	0	86.8 (VS)

Legend: 100-90: Outstanding (O); 85-89: Very Satisfactory (VS);80-84: Satisfactory (S);75-79: Fairly satisfactory (FS); 75 -below: Did not meet expectation

Furthermore, there were 22(9%) students who got the outstanding rating. Outstanding rating means they exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills and understanding the subject and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic task. Next were 96 (42%) pupils who obtained the very satisfactory rating, which means that they develop the fundamental knowledge, skills and understanding the subject and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic task. Followed by 89 (39%) pupils who obtained satisfactory level and 23(10%) of the pupils obtained Fairly satisfactory.

This reveals that majority of the pupil-participants had obtained the very satisfactory rating during school year 2022-2023. Very satisfactory rating means that students develop the fundamental knowledge, skills and understanding the subject and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic task. However, the academic achievement of the pupils should be enhanced since the highest is Outstanding. Teachers must still find ways to help the pupils improved their academic achievement.

Kim (2020) found that strategies like differentiated instruction, flexible grouping and cooperative learning were effective strategies for improving academic achievement of the students. As the data shown on the overall mean of the pupils' academic achievement, it signifies that teachers' classroom instruction should be enhanced by providing instructional modes that support best practices and extensive access to learning resources and can accommodate different learning styles and paces helps academic achievement of the pupils. Their strategies employed should provide intervention for some pupils while encouraging others to take their learning experience in exciting new directions; creates positive student attitudes about learning; promotes and improves productivity and skills that are vital both in the educational setting and in the workplace, teamwork, communication, presentation, and problem-solving; and breaks down physical and social barriers and reduces classroom isolation.

Problem 3. Is there a significant relationship between the classroom strategies used by multi-grade teachers in the differentiated instruction and academic achievement of the pupils?

To determine if significant relationship exists between the classroom strategies used by teachers and the academic achievement of the pupils, Pearson product correlation was performed. Moreover, Table 3 presents the results from two well- known tests of normality, namely the Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov – Smirnov tests. Since there were only 15 teacher-participants, a Shapiro-Wilk and Kolmogorov – Smirnov tests were used to test if the teachers' assessments on classroom strategies were normally distributed.

Looking at the p-value of classroom strategies, all the domains have greater than 0.05, which means that the population distribution is normal. This implies that the larger p-value or when p-value is greater than 0.05, the datum is normally distributed. Thus, correlation

was used because teachers' assessment on classroom strategies are normally distributed.

Table 3. *Tests of Normality*

	<i>Kolmogorov-Smirnova</i>			<i>Shapiro-Wilk</i>			<i>Interpretation</i>
	<i>Statistic</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	<i>Statistic</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Sig.</i>	
Differentiated Instruction	0.117	15	0.200*	0.963	15	0.688*	Significant
Cooperative Learning	0.234	15	0.321*	0.768	15	0.893*	Significant
Flexible Grouping	0.212	15	0.405*	0.866	15	0.543*	Significant

The correlation analysis was performed to examine the relationship among the pupils' academic achievement and the teachers' assessment on classroom strategies. Table 4 presents correlation coefficient, degree of correlation, p-value, and the remark of the analysis for each independent variable versus the dependent variable.

Table 4. *Correlation Coefficients and Significance of Relationship between the Classroom strategies used by Teachers and the Academic Achievement*

<i>Independent Variable</i>	<i>Dependent Variable: Academic Achievement</i>				
	<i>Correlation Coefficient</i>	<i>p-value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	
Differentiated Instruction	0.047	0.479	Accept	Not Significant	
Cooperative Learning	0.216**	0.032	Reject	Significant	
Flexible grouping	0.277**	0.000	Reject	Significant	

Legend: Very Weak- 0.0- 0.20; Weak-0.21- 0.40; Moderate-0.41-0. 60; Strong- 0.61-0. 80; Very Strong-0.81-1. 00
 **Significant at 0.05 level

This study's correlation analysis relies on various statistical assumptions. The first assumption is that the variables being studied have a linear relationship, where one variable change proportionally to another variable. Also, it assumes that the data used in the analysis are normally distributed and do not contain significant outliers as they can affect results negatively. Another important assumption of this analysis is there isn't any multicollinearity among these variables; hence they should not be highly correlated with each other for an accurate outcome.

Despite its usefulness, the correlation analysis approach employed in this study is not without limitations. Firstly, it's important to note that although a significant relationship between variables may be identified through this method, such relationships do not necessarily indicate cause and effect. Secondly, while correlation coefficients indicate direction and strength of interdependence among variables under scrutiny; they fail to provide information on the extent or practical applicability of these associations. Thirdly, confounding factors which could influence observed connections are neither accounted for nor adjusted in correlational analyses carried out within our framework here.

The study's findings suggest that cooperative learning and flexible grouping are positively correlated with pupils' academic achievement, whereas differentiated instruction is not. Nevertheless, caution should be exercised in interpreting these results since the correlation analysis approach has limitations. For instance, while the analysis establishes a significant association between cooperative learning and academic achievement, it fails to clarify why this connection exists or control for various other factors that may impact students' scholastic performance.

Moreover, the research underscores the necessity for educators to enhance their understanding and utilization of differentiated instruction. Even though no notable correlation with academic success was discovered, differentiated instruction remains a crucial pedagogical approach that may yield advantages beyond what this analysis could reveal. The obstacles encountered by teachers in incorporating differentiated instruction--such as limited time availability--underscore how intricate it can be to implement instructional methodologies effectively within actual classroom environments.

To sum up, correlation analysis can offer useful understanding of the connections between variables. However, it is crucial to acknowledge its constraints and interpret outcomes with care after examining other impacting elements. Furthermore, the research indicates implications for teacher coaching and assistance in executing efficient teaching methods within multi-grade classroom environments.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The teachers believed that classroom strategies like differentiated instruction, flexible grouping, and collaborative learning were very effective to the pupils for the improvement of their academic achievement. Differentiated instruction being the most effective followed by flexible groupings and then collaborative learning.

The pupils' academic achievement which is their average revealed that pupils develop the fundamental knowledge, skills and understanding the subject and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic task effectively by the used of these strategies.

Collaborative learning and flexible grouping has a p-value less than 0.05 which is lower than the significant level which implies that these has effect to the academic achievement of the pupils. This means, the higher the exposure or the knowledge of the teacher the higher the academic achievement of the pupils will be. Moreover, differentiated instruction has a p-value greater than the significant level which means it has no effect to the academic achievement of the pupils.

Relative to the findings and conclusion, the following recommendations were formulated:

Teachers should encourage the parents to actively involve in school's activities to foster students' learning. Also, teachers must establish an environment where students feel comfortable to approach and ask.

Teachers should take part in the school's programs and activities and familiarize themselves on the many aspects of children's schooling that they can be involved in. They must also create a supportive home environment for their children that support them in their learning activities.

Schools should provide more activities that increase the academic achievement of the students.

For future researchers who wish to enhance and/or use this study, the researchers suggest to consider the parents to be the respondents of the study as it may reveal a new perspective in understanding the relationship between classroom strategies and academic performance.

Professional Development Opportunities: Teachers should be provided with ongoing professional development opportunities focused on enhancing their understanding and implementation of differentiated instruction. Workshops, seminars, and collaborative learning communities can be valuable forums for sharing best practices, exploring innovative teaching strategies, and addressing challenges related to differentiation in multi-grade classrooms.

Curriculum Adaptations: Policymakers and curriculum developers should consider adaptations to the curriculum to better align with the principles of differentiated instruction. This may involve providing resources, materials, and instructional supports that cater to the diverse learning needs of students in multi-grade classrooms. Flexible curriculum frameworks that allow for individualized learning paths and varied instructional approaches can empower teachers to effectively implement differentiation strategies.

Supportive Learning Environments: Schools and educational institutions should prioritize creating supportive learning environments that foster collaboration, communication, and mutual support among teachers. Collaborative planning sessions, peer observations, and mentorship programs can facilitate the sharing of effective teaching practices and promote a culture of continuous improvement within multi-grade teaching teams.

Data-Informed Decision Making: Teachers should utilize assessment data to inform their instructional decisions and tailor their teaching approaches to meet the individual needs of students. Regular formative assessments, diagnostic tools, and progress monitoring measures can provide valuable insights into student learning gaps and inform the implementation of targeted interventions and differentiated instruction strategies.

Parent and Community Engagement: Policymakers should encourage partnerships between schools, parents, and the community to support student learning and academic achievement. Engaging parents as partners in education, providing resources for home learning activities, and involving community stakeholders in school-based initiatives can create a more holistic support system for students in multi-grade classrooms.

Research-Informed Practice: Teachers and policymakers should stay abreast of current research and best practices in multi-grade education, differentiated instruction, and effective classroom strategies. By grounding their decision-making and instructional approaches in evidence-based practices, educators can ensure that their efforts are aligned with the latest research findings and have the greatest impact on student learning outcomes.

References

Department of Education, Philippines. (1997, November 14). DO 96, S. 1997 – Policies and guidelines in the organization and operation of multigrade (MG) classes. Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/>

Department of Education, Philippines. (2009, July 24). DO 81, s. 2009 – Strengthening the Implementation of Multigrade Program in Philippine Education. Retrieved from <https://www.deped.gov.ph/>

Gardner, H. (1983). *Frames of Mind: The Theory of Multiple Intelligences*. Basic Books.

Hoffman, J. (2002)., Flexible Grouping Strategies in the Multiage Classroom. *Theory Into Practice*, 41(1), 47-52. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15430421tip4101_8

Karadağ Yılmaz, R., & Yeganeh, E. (2021). Who and How Do I Include? A Case Study on Teachers' Inclusive Education Practices. *International Journal of Progressive Education*, 17(2), 2021.

Kurt, S. (2020, July 11). *Vygotsky's Zone of Proximal Development and Scaffolding*. Title of Website. Retrieved Month Day, Year,

from <https://educationaltechnology.net/vygotskys-zone-of-proximal-development-and-scaffolding/>

Lenhoff, S. W., et.,al. (2020). The potential for multi-site literacy interventions to reduce summer slide among low-performing students. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 110,104806. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2020.10480>

Little, A. W. (2001). Multigrade teaching: Towards an international research and policy agenda. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 21(6), 481-497. Retrieved from <https://tinyurl.com/37rd5bw4>

Loes, C. N. (Year of publication). The Effect of Collaborative Learning on Academic Motivation. Title of Journal, Volume(Issue), Page range. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1340445.pdf>

Mbanaso, U. M., Abrahams, L., & Okafor, K. C. (Year). Research Philosophy, Design and Methodology Research Techniques for Computer Science, Information Systems and Cybersecurity. In Book Title (pp. 81–113).

National Center for Education Statistics. (2017). *NCES Handbook of Survey Methods*. Retrieved from <http://nces.ed.gov/nationsreportcard/>

National Center for Education Statistics. (n.d.). Scale Scores and NAEP Achievement Levels. The Nation's Report Card. Retrieved from https://nces.ed.gov/nationsreportcard/guides/scores_achv.aspx

Proehl, R. A., et.al.(March 2013). A Collaborative Approach: Assessing the Impact of Multi-Grade Classrooms. *Journal Name*, 16(2), 417-440. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1005662.pdf>

Rugutt, J. K., & Chemosit, C. C. (Year). A Study of Factors that Influence College Academic Achievement: A Structural Equation Modeling Approach. Title of Journal, Volume(Issue), Page range. Retrieved from <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ846830.pdf>

Springer. <https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-031-30031-86> Gera, M., Rathod, U., Karra-Aly, A., Aluckal, E., Abraham, A. (Year of Publication). Team Based Learning Vs Problem Based Learning in Medical Education: A Systematic Review. *European Journal of Medical Science*, 8(1), Article 3795. <https://doi.org/10.32677/ejms.v8i1.3795>

Tayoni and Aboejo (2023). The Multigrade Education Program: A Policy Evaluation. *International Journal of Academic Pedagogical Research (IJAPR)*, 7(1), 1-6. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369370422>

Team Based Learning Vs Problem Based Learning in Medical Education: A Systematic Review. *European Journal of Medical Science*, 8(1), Article 3795.

Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in Society: The Development of Higher Psychological Processes*. Harvard University Press.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Karen Gay P. Dy, PhD

Mindanao State University – Philippines

Aisah V. Boreros

Mindanao State University – Philippines

Ruskein D. Burlat

Mindanao State University – Philippines

Markhiesvel L. Dicalan

Mindanao State University – Philippines

Jaica R. Malon

Mindanao State University – Philippines

Manilyn M. Marturillas

Mindanao State University – Philippines